

Challenges of a Sales Manager Under Covid-19 Crises: A Case of Golden Pearl

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Abstract:- The outbreak of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) has severely affected the global and Pakistani economy. The negative impact of COVID-19 on business has been observed without exception. However, the density of the impact has varied across sectors, sub-sectors, business types, and firm size. In this case, the study researcher tries to identify the impact of Covid 19 on the sales and marketing operations of Golden Pearl Cosmetics. The other objective is to identify the impact of Covid 19 on managing customer experience and on operations sustainability. The method chosen for the case study is the qualitative research method. The examiner investigates perceptions and points of view in a circumstance since the structure of qualitative research is inductive. For this, the researcher conducts an interview with the operational manager of Golden Pearl Cosmetics. This case study was written for undergraduate classes of business and administrating students. It can be taught in courses on sales management, marketing management, and human resource management. The case study encourages students to conduct in-depth research on problems that occur in sales and marketing and the impact they may have on suppliers and buyers.

Keywords:- Sales, Marketing, Sales Operations, Management, Customer Experience, Communication, COVID-19

I. INTRODUCTION

With the arrival of Covid-19, Mr. Salman, the sales manager, and the marketing manager at Golden Pearl, Cosmetics, started to panic as many industrial sectors started facing an economic crisis. The year 2020 was predicted to be a year of great sales and expansion for the firm as they have planned different activities. Still, the pandemic continues to claim lives, and the global economy continues to decline, which has caused disruptions in terms of sales and marketing activities for the firm. Running a plant that relied on ground workers hired from several locations took work. Transportation and supply issues were causing disruptions that regularly ruined company assets in manufacturing the required shipments and order fulfillment. The unwillingness of the corporate environment to take the necessary action could have been improved by the more serious possibility of destructive labor shortages and shutdowns. People's purchasing power suffered during the first half of FY20 due to high inflation, rising energy prices,

and stringent economic stagnation. In contrast, the outbreak had a detrimental influence on sales and marketing. These business and trade practices affected the company's finances and management regarding upholding corporate duties and enabling critical talks and approvals to develop and be successfully completed. During this time, they encounter difficulties and obstacles with growth strategies as a result of decisions taken at the strategic level and in connection to marketing. Concentrating on how this decision was made and its results can aid in improving strategizing for company growth prospects and targeted company strategies.

II. KEY ISSUES FACING

A. Sustainable Operations

Mr. Salman, the Sales Manager's mind was whirling by early evening. He was aware that he needed to identify the main troublesome points in the way of sales operation as soon as possible and formulate a strategy to address them inside the overall framework of the operations function for golden pearl cosmetics in the Lahore region. The cosmetics business has been most negatively impacted since, during the pandemic, consumers started to entirely alter their priorities and behaviors, prioritizing hygiene, nutrition, and personal care items over cosmetic products. This shows the industry's ability to withstand the challenging FY20 and its effects during the nationwide shutdown brought on by the epidemic. Although the cosmetic industry has started to operate, online channels have raised significant demand. The firm's bottom line went negative in FY20. As revealed by the manager, the big distribution network spanning numerous sales channels started to diminish sales transparency. When working with a variety of market segments, the problem could have been more manageable. It took much work to keep track of direct sales for each of these. The necessary sales or clearance data was generally extracted from excess stock, which was then contrasted with revenue data. When data was received delayed, inaccurate, or both, it may not be feasible to account for defective or returned goods.

B. Managing Customer Experience

Variations in product catalogs, information, and graphics are quite frequent for companies or businesses using a hierarchical distribution approach. Each retailing or distributor associate may display the brand's products on various platforms and e-stores using their own text and imagery. Sometimes the distributors' listings need to employ more specifics, or the product data are presented as

unattractive. In the case of Golden Pearl, the arrival of the pandemic raised customer experience issues on online retail channels, which became a challenge to manage the products and consumer concerns due to a lack of accessibility. This resulted in an inconsistent message, which confused online customers, diluted their relationship with the company, and harmed the business's reputation. Additionally, customers will likely question the authenticity of the goods that these distribution partners are offering for sale. Customers want secure, dependable products when it comes to skincare, hair care, and cosmetics. If online product descriptions do not reflect this, firms risk losing sales to rivals that offer more attractive and interactive displays and information.

III. GOLDEN PEARL COSMETICS

One of Pakistan's top manufacturers of skincare and personal care products is Golden Pearl Cosmetics (Pvt.) Ltd. It was started in 1997 by the chairman, Mr Sheikh Abid Mehmood. Within Pakistan's skincare as well as whitening sector, Golden Pearl Cosmetics (Pvt) Ltd. is a trailblazer. To satisfy client demands, it has created its own special formulas. Golden Pearl Cosmetics (Pvt) Ltd began its operations in Chichawatni and afterward extended to Lahore in order to create a vast array of superior personal as well as cosmetic goods.

Golden Pearl Cosmetics reached its greatest and most significant mark in 2017 when it erected the second & greatest facilities for its industrial equipment cosmetics in Lahore. On the location of twenty-four canals, a manufacturing sector was built. To preserve the excellent quality of the items, raw materials are sourced from Spain, France, the United States, China, Malaysia, and Thailand.

We are constantly appreciative of our clients' continuing support. With its distinctive line of skincare and beauty items, Golden Pearl Cosmetics (Pvt.) Ltd. has strongly entrenched itself as the top seller in modern days. However, during the period of the pandemic, staying at the top with sales and marketing became a headache for the managers in this regard. Golden Pearl Cosmetics believes that by applying the subject "Beauty Forever," it is possible to develop skincare items that will not only enhance the personalities of our customers but also foster a culture of beauty and skincare across the community. Golden Pearl Cosmetics (Pvt.) Ltd. is devoted to spreading the pleasure of elegance to as many individuals as possible in a variety of methods as they take a look ahead.

➤ Objectives

The main objectives of the firm are mentioned below:

- *To Identify the Impact of Covid-19 on Sales And Marketing Operations in an Organization.*
- *To Identify the Impact of Covid-19 on Managing the Customer Experience.*
- *To Identify the Impact of Covid-19 on Keeping the Operations Sustainable*

IV. CASE USE AND TAGET AUDIENCE

This case study was written for undergraduate classes of business and administrating students. It can be taught in courses on sales management, marketing management, and human resource management. The problems, in this case, are specific to a particular region. The case study encourages students to conduct in-depth research on problems that occur in sales and marketing and the impact they may have on suppliers and buyers.

➤ Highlighting Questions

- *What are the significant issues at Golden Pearl and the reasons for them.?*
- *What measures should the salesperson take to continue sustainable operations?*
- *In order to improve customer experience, what particular steps should he take?*

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The method chosen for the case study is the qualitative research method. The examiner investigates perceptions and points of view in a circumstance since the structure of qualitative research is inductive. Moreover, for this purpose, the interview technique is used. There is just one interview at a time with a particular participant. In essence, this is a tool that allows you to get more data about the topic.

VI. CONCLUSION

This case study is about the operational issues that occurred in Golden Pearl, leading to the impact on the sales of the firm from the perspective of a pandemic. The organization faced many ups and down during that tenure, but due to different decisions regarding managing consumers, and sustainability efforts, Mr. Salman somehow arranged to manage their sales network. Mr. Salman plays an important part in this scenario since he can interact with significantly greater, participate in significant choices, and support the firm sustainability. In this instance, the company's capacity to resist the difficult FY20 and its repercussions during the epidemic-caused nationwide shutdown. Mr. Salman's issue arose from the need to keep everyone in line during the virus slow down and meet the needs of the appropriate authorities.

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